

IN CONFIDENCE

NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL

DIRECTORATE OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

ATMOSPHERIC SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY BOARD

BRITISH ATMOSPHERIC DATA CENTRE (BADC) STEERING COMMITTEE

Twelfth meeting of the British Atmospheric Data Centre (BADC) Steering Group, 10:30 am, Friday 19th January 2001, Conference Room 1, Space Science and Technology Department, Rutherford Appleton Laboratory.

AGENDA

1. Apologies
2. Report of the eleventh meeting of the Group
3. Matters arising from the report of the eleventh meeting
4. BADC progress report, including status report in view of next Output and Performance Measures (OPM)
5. Data Centres Review
6. NERC Metadata Gateway
7. Overview of current topical matters by BADC staff
8. Any other business
9. Date of next meeting

NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL

SCIENCE PROGRAMMES DIRECTORATE

ATMOSPHERIC SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY BOARD

BRITISH ATMOSPHERIC DATA CENTRE (BADC) STEERING COMMITTEE

Role, Terms of Reference and Membership

1 Role

The Steering Committee shall provide guidance and advice to BADC, the NERC Head of Atmospheric Science, the NERC Director Science Programmes and the NERC Science and Technology Board (STB), as appropriate, on all aspects of atmospheric data.

The Steering Committee shall assist STB in formulating future requirements for BADC, and provide guidance to the BADC to enable it to fulfil its role in the atmospheric community, consistent with the NERC Science Strategy and the NERC data policy.

2 Terms of Reference

The Steering Committee shall:

- i) advise the NERC on the future development of BADC;
- ii) assist the BADC in establishing its priorities against the scientific objectives and within the resource allocations set by STB;
- iii) oversee the overall BADC activity and management and receive regular reports from BADC in accordance with the NERC Service Level Agreement with Rutherford Appleton Laboratory;
- iv) implement mechanisms for regular assessment of BADC performance (quinquennial review);
- v) implement mechanisms for selecting datasets and services to be offered by BADC;
- vi) advise NERC on the requirements of BADC for computing facilities and capital equipment;
- vii) evaluate future BADC funding proposals prior to submission to NERC;
- viii) ensure a close and effective liaison between BADC and NERC STB, relevant national and international programmes and funding agencies.

- ix) assist BADC, where possible, to identify and express user requirements for BADC;
- x) ensure the implementation of data management plans in accordance with the NERC Data Policy within the resources available;
- xi) ensure adherence to the NERC Exploitation Policy, if and when appropriate;
- xii) report as required to Council, normally on a financial year basis.

3 Membership

Prof P. J. Valdes, chair	University of Reading
Dr H. Böttger	ECMWF
Prof K. A. Browning	University of Reading
Mr N. R. Collins	NERC
Dr R. A. Cox	University of Cambridge
Dr C. Hall	Met Office
Dr B. N. Lawrence	Head BADC, <i>Ex Officio</i>
Dr C. Reeves	UEA, ACSOE
Dr G. Vaughan	University of Wales, Aberystwyth
Dr B. J. Whitaker	University of Leeds

Dr J. Slingo, former chair person, and Dr G. Carver have resigned from the Committee.
 Dr L. Gray has been replaced by Dr B. Lawrence at the head of the BADC.

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BRITISH ATMOSPHERIC DATA CENTRE (BADC) STEERING COMMITTEE

Agenda Item 2. Report of the eleventh meeting of the BADC Steering Committee.

The report of the eleventh meeting of the BADC Steering Committee is attached. The Committee is asked to approve the report.

Agenda Item 3. Matters arising from the report of the eleventh meeting.

Actions continued from the report of the tenth meeting were:

- **N. Collins** to investigate possible BADC representation on the ad hoc NERC/Met Office Joint Panel on Aircraft Operation.
- **N. Collins** to investigate possible BADC representation in thematic programmes steering committees and allocation of part of the programmes budget to data custody.
- **B. Lawrence** to ensure liaison and collaboration with SPARC.

Actions in the report of the last meeting were:

1. **B. Lawrence** to include funding issue in 5-year plan document.
2. **B. Lawrence** to consider possible inclusion in 5-year plan document of statistics of users' queries by discipline.
3. **N. Collins** to investigate the setting up of a formal mechanism to make BADC aware of all potential data coming out of NERC funded atmospheric research.
4. **N. Collins** to explore the possibility of implementing a new funding scheme.

5. **B. Lawrence** to write letters to Review Panel, Data Centres review groups and Bob Guerny (Reading) about EO data.
6. **B. Lawrence** to emphasize DARC-BADC relationship in 5-year plan document.
7. **B. Lawrence** to add COSMAS to the list of new thematic programmes.
8. **B. Lawrence** to get in touch with DARC about a possible representation in BADC Steering Committee.
9. **B. Lawrence** to add SIZE in 5-year plan document.
10. **B. Lawrence** to update 5-year plan so that reference is made to programmes in a generic sense rather than to thematic programmes (in order to include core strategic programmes like UGAMP).
11. **B. Lawrence** to ask for more money for middleware in 5-year plan document.
12. **B. Lawrence** to include explicit clarification about staff allocation for chemistry support in 5-year plan document.
13. **B. Lawrence** to request funding for an additional tape driver by 2004, in 5-year plan document.
14. **B. Lawrence** to ask for supporting letters from the Met Office and ECMWF in view of the review process.

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BRITISH ATMOSPHERIC DATA CENTRE (BADC) STEERING COMMITTEE

Minutes of the eleventh meeting of the BADC Steering Committee, held at the Medical Research Centre, London, on September 8th, 2000. Meeting start time: 10:30 am.

Present:

Dr P. Valdes, chair	(PV)	Reading
Dr H. Böttger	(HB)	ECMWF
Mr N. Collins	(NC)	NERC
Dr T. Cox	(TC)	Cambridge
Ms A. De Rudder	(ADR)	BADC
Dr C. Dimmer	(CD)	NERC
Dr L. Gray	(LG)	CLRC
Dr C. Hall	(CH)	UKMO
Dr B. Lawrence	(BL)	BADC
Dr S. Pepler	(SP)	BADC
Dr C. Reeves	(CR)	UEA
Pr J. Slingo	(JS)	Reading
Dr G. Vaughan	(GV)	Aberystwyth

1. Apologies

Pr K.R. Browning (Reading), Dr B. Whitaker (Leeds).

NC commented on the changes in the Steering Committee (SC) membership. Dr B. Whitaker (Leeds) is joining the SC. This is hoped to provide some continuity with the CAST project. Dr G. Carver has resigned from the SC.

2. Report of the tenth meeting

Response to action items:

- 3.5 BADC representation on the ad hoc NERC/Met Office Joint Panel on Aircraft Operation. [Action: NC — continues.]
- 3.6 BADC representation in thematic programmes steering committees and allocation of part of the thematic programmes budget to data custody. Objective not achieved yet. [Action: NC — continues.]

- 3.10 SPARC liaison and collaboration. [Action: BL — continues.]
- 3.11 Meteosat mirroring occurs on a routine basis. [Action: ADR — completed.]
- 3.12 Plan future strategy in line with increased usage. [Action: SC — dealt with as part of review document (see below).]
TC commented on the negative impression users would get if more users were turned down on the grounds of support funding.
- 8.3 BADC review and proposal for the next 5-year plan. [Action: BL — document written.] (See next section).

3. BADC review

JS and LG were thanked by the SC for their past active presence and achievements as BADC head and BADC SC chair. The SC welcomed BL as the new BADC head.

The BADC review will take place at RAL on the 2nd of October. The result of the review will hopefully confirm level funding by the end of October. The review report will then be passed to the Science and Technology Board data centre review in February, which will grant any increase.

The key points of the draft of the BADC review and strategy plan, to be submitted in its achieved form to the Review Panel in October, were summarised and presented by BL, for discussion by the SC members, but a question about DAFESS was first raised by CR. BL gave some explanations about the concept (to be addressed in more detail below — see Section 3.4).

3.1 Current usage

Stress was placed on the increase in data sets volume, that will most likely have to be faced in 2½ years.

The number of BADC users has been steadily increasing. A graph of users number versus time prompted some discussion as to how many users were still "active". SP estimated that this number is likely to be about half the number of registered users. Unregistering of inactive users is currently only done 5 years after registration.

BL commented the breakdown by users' discipline, showing that approximately half of the users are not from the Atmospheric Science and Technology Board (ASTB) supported fields. This statement raised the funding issue, that will need to be brought up in the review. A data centre funding line might have to be set up. In this context, TC underlined the likely future arising of "crossed disciplines" data centres and expressed a general warning against the threat that would be represented by merging all DC into a single one. The opinion of the SC is in favour of maintaining individual DC with a strong

community based identity and improving liaison between them, which could be achieved in centralising coordination at a designated DC.

[Action 1: BL — funding issue to be included in 5-year plan document.]

The number of users' queries is also increasing, with a marked majority of queries from non-ASTB origin, related to inexperience with data types and formats. JS pointed out the significance of statistics of users' queries by discipline. JS also underlined the need to assist the greater numbers of inexperienced users in data formatting, data fetching, etc, and the importance of meeting school queries by setting up tutorials, etc.

[Action 2: BL — consider possible inclusion in review document of statistics of users' queries by discipline.]

3.2 Upcoming opportunities

As an introduction, BL raised the question of unused or unpublicized atmospheric data sitting in various universities or laboratories. How could BADC manage to become aware of their existence and get them? Some systematic "data archaeology" activity should be undertaken by BADC (concept developed in 5-year plan document).

Regarding the current and future thematic programmes, LG pointed out that the answer would be to get BADC involved in the programmes from their start. CR pointed out that no procedure is set up to chase up non-compliance with NERC data policy.

[Action 3: NC — A formal mechanism needs to be set up to make the BADC aware of all potential data coming out of NERC funded atmospheric research.]

A discussion started about difficulties met with the current data management funding system, ensured via NERC grants. Various possible funding schemes were overviewed. BL suggested that scientists would be encouraged to resort to BADC services by being offered additional science funding in proportion to the money spent on data management. NC suggested a "top-slicing" model (some percentage of the programmes budget would automatically be devoted to data management). It was underlined however that the latter would be unfair to programmes involving little or no data management at all. NC then concluded that some combination of the two would probably be the most appropriate approach.

[Action 4: NC — explore possibilities of implementing new funding scheme.]

BL presented and commented a list of upcoming programmes and projects in which BADC could play a role.

➤ EOS.

BL expressed concerns about ocean data, that are at present not catered for within NERC DC.

[Action 5: BL — letters to Review Panel, DC review groups and Bob Guerny (Reading) about EO data.]

➤ **HiRDLS.**

Here it was stressed that DC should not necessarily hold all the data listed in their catalogue, but should definitely offer an access to them.

A digression was made about DAFESS. It was agreed that the BADC should present DAFESS as a pilot project to the review panel.

➤ **DARC (Data Assimilation Research Centre).**

The role of BADC should be to provide the input observational data and, more importantly, to host the output assimilated data and offer the scientists' community an access to them, since they are likely to be very popular.

LG insisted on the fact that no real time assimilation should be performed as part of the normal BADC routine (i.e. without extra funding).

JS would like the requirement for a stronger connection between DARC and BADC to appear in the document.

[Action 6: BL — emphasize DARC–BADC relationship in 5-year plan document.]

A digression on the funding issue took place again.

➤ **Envisat.**

BADC could act as the distribution point of Envisat data to the UK research community.

➤ **UWERN.**

➤ **MADRAS.**

➤ **Tyndall Centre.**

The role of BADC could be to catalogue their data.

➤ **ERA40.**

➤ **E-grid.**

There is a vast amount of money for the e-grid project. This is not just about distributed processing but also distributed storage. If the BADC is not involved with e-grid we risk being replaced by it.

➤ **New thematic programmes.**

COSMAS should be added to BL's list.

[Action 7: BL — add COSMAS to the list of new thematic programmes.]

LG suggested that a representative of each of the main thematic programmes (and definitely of DARC) should be invited to sit on the BADC SC – to ensure a good communication about data management issues.

[Action 8: BL — get in touch with DARC about a possible representation in BADC SC.]

COAPEC. We have an agreement with the COAPEC core team.

PRESCIENT. Geological data and model output will be archived at BGS. Data may be distributed via BADC or UEA Link programme.

SIZE (Sea Ice Zone Emissions). Should be added to the list.

[Action 9: BL — add SIZE in 5-year plan document.]

TC noted that the review document needs to refer to programmes in a generic sense rather than to thematic programmes if it is to include core strategic programmes like UGAMP.

[Action 10: BL — update document accordingly (refer to programmes in a generic sense).]

3.3 Five-year plan: the “business as usual” proposal

The following work packages encapsulate the BADC activities.

CWP01 - Retrieval and distribution of Met. data.

CWP02 - Retrieval and distribution of NWP data.

CWP03 - User support.

CWP04 - Infrastructure and cataloguing.

This would also include (in the long term) implementation of a system to extract subsets of data sets.

CWP05 - Atmospheric chemistry support.

The BADC would like to offer a number of standard atmospheric parameters and data for atmospheric modelling, such as spectroscopic data, standard profiles of de-coupled contributions to heating rate and ozone destruction rate, etc. Possibly also online tools to compute some of these parameters for various conditions.

TC commented that there is a great deal of change in atmospheric chemistry data, with a shift from printed data books to electronic versions (in particular, for JPL reaction rates).

CWP06 - Community support.

CWP07 - Data archaeology.

CWP08 - Middleware.

The BADC intends to develop additional online services following the model of the very popular trajectory calculator.

Use of BADC by UGAMP has been limited in the past but it is likely to change with the introduction of more middleware. Some of the functions Paul Berrisford fulfils in Reading would be more appropriately transferred to BADC.

[Action 11: BL — More money needs to be asked for middleware in the 5-year plan document.]

CWP09 – Liaison.

It was suggested in the past that BADC funded activities based in universities may help facilitate data ingestion and distribution. BL's opinion is that this is impractical given the current level of funding.

Liaison with the other DC should be improved.

CWP10 – Research within BADC.

NC would like a more detailed research proposal to appear in the document.

It was agreed that a full research proposal could not be produced in the time available, but more details of what was planned could be included.

BL would like to get involved in data assimilation. The BADC data resource offers a good opportunity for research studies in this field.

BL then displayed the BADC organization chart and the staff allocation table. It was felt that the proposed staff allocation of 0.85 staff years to the chemistry support was on the low side, although it was acknowledged that this would be topped up with money from thematic programmes like URGENT.

[Action 12: BL — add explicit clarification about staff allocation for chemistry support in the review document.]

CR underlined the need of ensuring continuity in the identity of staff members.

3.4 Five-year plan: the DAFESS proposal

DAFESS would address the issue raised by the fact that the NERC catalogue allows metadata search and consultation but not actual data download. Catalogue interoperability is the first step into a wider ranging interoperability that is the heart of the DAFESS proposal. When operational, DAFESS should allow data extraction and sub-setting from multiple data centres using a single access point, as well as format-to-format translation. This facility would meet the scientists' increasing need to fetch data from various locations and in various formats (for example, it would help researchers interested in processes occurring at the interface of two systems such as land/atmosphere, ocean/atmosphere, atmosphere/biosphere, etc).

DAFESS should be presented to the Review Panel as a pilot project launched by BADC, that could for example be the object of a 3-year contract for BADC, after which it could attract its own funding and become autonomous. It would start with one partner (for example SOC), then progressively expand to involve other DC. Involved staff would include 1½ person at BADC (one person for the technical work and half a person for the coordination work) and one person at the partner institution.

3.5 Finance

GV supported the idea of devoting part of the budget to finance the Summer School on atmospheric data processing and use.

Hardware cost predictions need to be included in the review document so that NERC should be ready to meet announced requests.

[Action 13: BL — Funding for an additional tape drive by 2004 should be explicitly requested in document.]

4. Other

[Action 14: BL — Supporting letters from the Met Office and ECMWF need to be acquired for the review process.]

5. Report on Met. data

UKMO. BL gave a brief report on the current state of the UKMO Unified Model data. The hardware for automatic acquiring of data is now in place and test retrievals have been performed. In order to reduce the impact on UKMO, it will be necessary to optimize the procedure. UM is one of the BADC top priorities — should be operational by Christmas.

ECMWF. HB drew the SC members' attention onto two new online features: a revised ECMWF data user guide and updated documentation on the model. ERA40 will be available on isentropic levels.

6. Date of next meeting

End of January or early February 2001.

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Agenda Item 4. BADC Progress Report and status report for OPM.

The progress report of the BADC team is enclosed. The Steering Committee are asked to approve the report.

**The British Atmospheric Data Centre
Progress Report (April 2000 - January 2001)**

January 2001

1. Highlights

- *Unified Model data extracted from the Met Office Weekly.*
- *Web trajectory service very popular; 100,000 trajectories launched.*
- *User database now more integrated into infrastructure; Web interface to user data allows users to check their own details and dataset permissions.*
- *Data from UTLS and URGENT programmes continues to be regularly ingested; BADC staff remain in close contact with researchers.*
- *Registered BADC users increased to 1300.*
- *590 substantial user queries serviced from January 1999 to January 2000.*
- *New workstation inside the Met office network to facilitate access to UM and other Met Office data sets.*
- *Funding and work agreed for the BADC involvement in the COAPEC thematic programme.*
- *The BADC is gearing up for e-science; funding from CLRC e-science budget will place the BADC in good position for e-science initiatives.*

2. Work packages

2.1 CWP01: Acquisition of synoptic observational meteorological data.

2.1.1 MIDAS Land surface station data

This data set consists of daily and hourly surface weather observations from the Met Office station network, extracted from the MIDAS database. This data set was updated weekly until July 2000, when a change in the MIDAS data structure and underlying database halted the normal extraction procedures. The BADC can now extract data from the new Oracle MIDAS, but this is inconsistent with the previously extracted data. Solving the problems resulting from this will be a priority in the coming months.

In the meantime, a “special request data service” has been put in place to satisfy the demand from BADC users. This service appears to be highly successful as data extracted corresponds to the exact need of individual users (e.g. parameters for specific station and specific time period), however it is very labour intensive.

2.1.2 MIDAS Marine data

Marine surface data from buoy and ship measurements were obtained during MIDAS’s move to Oracle. Text files produced to transfer the data for one system to the other were copied to the BADC. The data have not been released, as yet, because of the considerable effort needed to document and sort the data into a usable form.

2.1.3 MetDB Global Radiosonde data

Global Radiosonde data from the Met Office MetDB continue to be updated automatically.

2.1.4 MetDB Global Synoptic data:

From the BADC Users Survey of June 2000, it clearly appeared that worldwide synoptic data is one of the most wanted data set. The BADC is now working on extracting worldwide synoptic data reports from the MetDB on a routine basis. Synoptic data reports have already been successfully retrieved from the MetDB upon a special user request for the JET2000 campaign. The weekly synoptic data extraction from the MetDB should be made operational by March 2001. Relevant data set documentation will be provided accordingly.

2.1.5 Assimilated data

Global stratospheric analyses for the UARS period (1991- the present) are automatically updated daily from the Met Office. The transition to the 3D variational (3DVAR) data assimilation system to replace the Analysis Correction (AC) data assimilation system on 14 November 2000 was smooth. The assimilated data set web pages are currently being revised to include information relative to the 3DVAR data assimilation system. This data set continues to be very heavily used.

2.1.6 Hadley centre data

The GISST, GICE, MOHSST6, MOHMAT4N, Central England Temperature and HADRT data from the Met Office have been updated every month during the year. A small error in the Hadley Centre's processing of the GISST data resulted in the BADC replacing this data set with a revised version.

2.1.5 Meteosat

Meteosat images of Europe continue to be mirrored from the University of Nottingham.

2.1.7 Jet2000

This NERC funded project capitalised on the fact that in the summer of 2000 the MRF C-130 aircraft was stationed in Cape Verde, and was available to make observations over West Africa. Data from aircraft measurements are already archived at the BADC. Met Office station data have also been extracted for the project by BADC staff. Dropsonde, video footage and satellite imagery will also be archived.

2.2 CWP02: Acquisition of NWP data from the UKMO and the ECMWF

2.2.1 ECMWF

Both the 2.5 and 1.125 degree gridded data sets continue to be updated automatically. A number of special requests have also been serviced via the MARS system. Forecast data was supplied to a number of field campaigns for planning purposes.

2.2.2 Unified Model

The process for routinely extracting UM model data has been in place since October 2000. Data are written to tape twice each day by a BADC workstation in the Met Office operations room. This produces a total data rate for global and mesoscale files of approximately 10 GB per day. Once the tapes are full (50 GB), the tapes are sent to the BADC.

Routines to read the UM data are currently being written. By the end of January the appropriate documentation and software should be ready and the data can be released. Some sections of the community will require the ability to generate UM start dumps from our archived fields. Once we have released the data we will look into the issues associated with this.

2.3 CWP03: User Support

The BADC provides support to its users by both e-mail and telephone. A total of 590 significant user queries have been serviced during the period January 2000 to January 2001. Some queries can require a substantial amount of effort - for example a request for a specific piece of data to be extracted from the Met Office archives or maintenance of Data Ordering Service.

Better documentation has reduced the number of queries by about 75% (compared to 1999) in areas such as file formats, data documentation and file transfer. Unfortunately queries about data availability and access permissions have risen by a factor of 4. This can be attributed to the problems with the MIDAS surface station data.

Over 1300 users are now registered at the BADC. To mark the 1000th registered user at the BADC, a press release was put out in June 2000.

2.4 CWP04: System Infrastructure

2.4.1 Web

The change to the Apache "mod_perl" server has improved the look of the BADC pages. The new server enabled the move away from frames and thus made bookmarking possible. Web pages continue to be updated as needed.

2.4.2 Registration

The handling of user registration information at the BADC has been gradually improved over the past year, with further improvements planned for 2001. The aim is to simplify the registration process for both external users and BADC staff. Users are now able to register for access to MST data online, without requiring any effort from BADC staff. This will be extended to other appropriate data sets during 2001.

The web interface to the data sets has been updated to allow users to both view their personal details and list the data sets that they have been granted access to.

2.4.3 Ingestion

The file ingestion system allows automated or semi-automated processing of data files that are submitted to the BADC. The ingestion system is now being used for seven different data sets, including UTLS and URGENT. The 'file uploader', which was originally written to allow users to submit NASA-Ames format files to us via a web page, has been re-written to make it more general purpose. It is now being used for uploading several different file types for the URGENT project, including images and metadata information.

2.5 CWP05: Atmospheric Chemistry support

2.5.1 IUPAC

The BADC documentation on the *IUPAC Summary of Evaluated Gas Kinetic and Photochemical Data for Atmospheric Chemistry* has been updated following the recent issue of the last evaluation and of the last version of the Web summary (December 2000).

2.5.2 ACSOE

Since last January, all data have been released to the public domain except ozone profiles posterior to 24 August 1998. The released data include observations onboard the C-130 aircraft, ozone profiles prior to 24 August 1998 and observations performed during the EAE (96 & 97), EASE (96 & 97), HILLCLOUD (96 & 97) and FREETEX (96 & 98) campaigns. The last ozone profiles will be progressively released between March and July 2001.

2.5.3 GOME

GOME data has been updated during the year. Complimentary cloud products derived from ATSR images are also available.

2.5.4 VIRTEM

The BADC is providing an archive and project web-site to the VIRTEM project funded under the EU 4th framework programme. Data from the MSF at RAL have been added to the archive. Groups in France and Germany have data ready to add.

2.5.5 UARS Data from the UARS chemistry instruments:

CLAES, ISAMS and MLS data are available as level 3 products and HALOE level 2 data are updated every night from the archive at NASA Langley. HALOE level 3 data is now also being routinely mirrored at BADC from NASA Langley.

2.5.6 FIRETRACC/100

FIRETRACC/100 is an EU funded project to trace the chemistry of the atmosphere over the last 100 years using ice cores. The BADC has been sub-contracted to do the archive and web site for the project. The web pages are complete, but we are still awaiting the data.

2.5.7 ESA Water Vapour

The European Space Agency funded a detailed study of the spectrum of water vapour to aid retrieval from GOME and SCIAMACHY. This small data set was archived at the BADC in August, but has already been downloaded hundreds of times.

2.6 WP06 Services and CAST

2.6.1 CAST

A new version of the CAST web site has been installed on the BADC server. Work is ongoing to get all the functionality of the original site operational at its new location. Once this is complete integration of BADC and CAST services can begin.

2.6.2 NASA-Ames plotter

The NASA-Ames plotter, which allows users to plot out the contents of NASA-Ames format files via a web interface, has been improved following requests from users. The

plotter can now plot any variable against any other variable, and points can be excluded from the plot in a more flexible manner than was previously possible.

2.6.3 *Formats and Coordinate Systems*

Online help on NASA Ames format has been gathered together and is now available from a single *Formats* page accessible from the *Services* section. This service is intended to be expanded in the future to include information and tools related to other formats (NetCDF, GRIB, GIF, etc).

Following queries from users, links to documentation on the Ordnance Survey reference system and to online converters (longitude, latitude from/to OS reference) are now available from a new Web page called *Coordinate Systems*. This service should also be developed to include information on other referentials (transformation formulas, etc) and calculations related to particular Earth coordinate systems (following a couple of queries, a formula giving the surface area of a grid cell in spherical coordinates has already been included).

2.6.4 *Highlighted Sites*

New *Highlighted Sites* pages have been written by Miss Lydia Henderson, a summer student who temporarily worked at BADC. Topics include *Tropospheric pollution*, *Storms* and *Environmental policy*. These pages are currently being reviewed and should come online soon.

2.6.5 *Trajectory service*

The WWW trajectory model has continued to be popular. Since March there have been 421 users of the trajectory service, submitting 5000 jobs and calculating nearly 100000 trajectories.

2.7 *CWP07: Data Archaeology*

2.7.1 *High Resolution Radiosonde data*

High resolution data is now available for Aberporth, Aughton, Boulmer, Camborne, Hemsby, Herstmonceux, Hillsborough, Lerwick and Stornoway. A practical update route from this data set is the next planned step.

2.7.2 *MST Radar Doppler spectra files*

The NERC MST radar's lowest level products are the Doppler spectra files. The MSTR project stores these raw files on CD. In order to increase the accessibility and produce another backup of the data, the CDs have been transcribed to the BADC tape library

2.7.3 *NIMROD rain fall data*

The Met Office NIMROD rain data is a combination of rain radar and NWP products. Interest in a gridded rainfall product has been shown in a number of queries. Trial data has been retrieved and some simple plots produced. Provisional agreement that the BADC may distribute this data has been approved.

2.7.4 MSF

Distribution of data from the NERC Molecular spectroscopy facility via the BADC has been discussed with MSF staff. We have already distributed the EAS water vapour data for them.

2.8 WP08: UTLS

Jamie Kettleborough has moved from full time BADC to 10% BADC and 90% research. Kevin Marsh has been newly recruited by the BADC and has become the primary contact between the BADC and the UTLS-Ozone community. More data is expected soon, particularly from the Egret campaign, which is now ready to submit its data.

EXPORT is an EU campaign in which UK participation was partly funded by UTLS. The EXPORT archive has been established as a separate data set at the BADC.

The trajectory service developed for UTLS continues to be well-used (see 2.6.5).

2.9 CWP09: Liaison with other data centres

A good deal of liaison with other NERC data centres has been done via the Data Management and Quality Assurance Committee of URGENT (See 2.11).

BADC has been solicited to take part to a project to develop a bilingual English/Russian Portal for Atmospheric Science, in collaboration with Russian scientists. This has resulted in the issue of a proposal submitted to INTAS in October 2000. INTAS is an emanation from the European Commission that aims at promoting East-West scientific cooperation. A decision regarding the acceptance of the project should be made by February or March, so that an early start date would be April 2001. Participation of the BADC to this project is relatively limited.

2.10 CWP10 Allied Research

Under the current budget, the BADC has £60K per annum allocated to support the research costs of the Head and to support one full time researcher. This funding has been used to contribute in three areas. Firstly, the research position was filled by Lesley Gray until October 1st; secondly, Bryan Lawrence has been establishing his personal research programme, primarily by supporting his graduate students; and thirdly, we have been investigating the installation of a Beowulf cluster at the BADC in conjunction with Myles Allen.

The research position is currently vacant, with an advertisement due out shortly, in conjunction with the advertisement of a COAPEC researcher. As advised previously, the BADC scientist will be appointed either in the area of data assimilation or physical parameterisations.

The salary savings for the intervening period will be used to provide a one-year salary for Mr Sam Dean so he can complete the final year of his University of Canterbury Ph.D. in the U.K. under Bryan Lawrence's direct supervision. Mr Dean is working on comparing simulations of, and observations of, orographic clouds. Mr Dean has already spent six weeks in October in the U.K. funded by Bryan Lawrence's NZ Marsden fund grant: "Gravity Wave Processes in the Atmosphere". This grant also supported a two-week visit by Bryan Lawrence to Christchurch to continue the supervision of the other four graduate students. Depending on the date of appointment of the data assimilation person, BADC funding may be used to support others of Bryan Lawrence's graduate students for short visits to the U.K. (Ms Mohar Chattopadhyay will be visiting RAL for three weeks from late January partly funded by the Marsden fund and partly by the BADC).

The third aspect of the BADC research programme will be the impending purchase of a Beowulf cluster, funded by a Myles Allen NERC equipment grant, the BADC, and the BADC research budget. The Beowulf cluster is being installed for a variety of reasons: it is needed in the short term by the climateprediction.com COAPEC project, in the medium term to support BADC research, and in the longer term it is intended that the cluster be used to provide the computing necessary for BADC users to be able to process large met data sets at the BADC rather than transfer the entire datasets to their home computing resources.

2.10.1 Studies undertaken by Dr Gray

Studies of the influence of the equatorial region on variability of the Northern Hemisphere (NH) stratospheric winter circulation have been carried out. Some NH winters are extremely disturbed and are accompanied by major stratospheric warmings, in which the polar temperatures rise by 20K or more in just a few days. In contrast, other winters have fewer warming events and the polar vortex remains cold and undisturbed. This variability is known to be influenced by the quasi biennial oscillation (QBO), an oscillation of the lower stratospheric equatorial winds from easterly to westerly with a period of approximately 2 years, although the precise mechanism (and its interaction with the solar cycle influence) is still poorly understood.

Stratospheric analyses have been used in conjunction with radiosonde and rocketsonde observations of the equatorial lower stratosphere to investigate the height dependence of the polar sensitivity to equatorial winds. This analysis has shown, for the first time, the sensitivity of polar warmings to winds throughout the whole depth of the equatorial stratosphere and not just to the lower stratospheric winds, as previously assumed. The data record of 25 years of rocketsonde observations (1963/64 - 1986/87) and 45 years of radiosonde data (1955/56 - 1999/2000) have also enabled an examination of the interaction of the QBO with the solar cycle influence. This data study has prompted a series of simple model simulations in order to simulate the observed behaviour, so that the precise mechanisms of influence and interaction may be investigated.

This work has been presented at the recent SPARC Assembly in Argentina (November 2000). It will also be presented (invited reviews) at both the forthcoming EGS meeting (Nice, March 2001) and IAMAS Assembly (Innsbruck, July 2001).

2.10.2 Publications

Gray, L.J., S.J. Phipps, T.J. Dunkerton, M.P. Baldwin, E.F. Drysdale and M.R. Allen, 2001. The influence of the equatorial upper stratosphere on northern hemisphere stratospheric sudden warmings. Q.J. Roy. Met. Soc. In revision.

Gray, L.J., E.F. Drysdale, T.J. Dunkerton and B.N. Lawrence, 2001. On the inter annual variability of the northern hemisphere stratospheric winter circulation: the role of the quasi biennial oscillation. Q.J. Roy. Met. Soc. In revision.

Osprey, S.M., B.N. Lawrence. A possible mechanism for in situ forcing of planetary waves in the summer extratropical mesosphere, Accepted pending minor revisions, Geophys. Res. Lett. (2001).

2.11 WP11 URGENT

A great deal of the work achieved in the framework of URGENT has been devoted to the coordination with the other three involved data centres (CEH Wallingford, CEH Monks Wood and BGS), *via* the Data Management and Quality Assurance (DMQA) Committee meetings, and to the collection of Data Management Plans from principal investigators (NERC requirement). A common URGENT Data Protocol has been established. The protocol has to be signed by anyone applying for access to the Air URGENT archive (access is restricted to URGENT participants; data will be released to the public domain one year after the end of each project).

An URGENT Air Web site has been set up and linked to the central URGENT gateway. This site includes the traditional BADC data set front page and a variety of documents and tools to help (1) data providers in formatting and submitting data and (2) data users in identifying and downloading the data they look for. These last features include project outlines, data summaries (directly accessible from the archive), a general inventory of recorded physico-chemical variables and a “clickable” site map of PUMA stations.

Among the 13 “air” projects within URGENT, 8 will deliver shared data — the other ones will produce software, recommendations to urban planners or confidential data (*Thermal climatology of West Midlands*). One of these 8 projects (*Organics in airborne particles*) is finished but has not submitted data yet. Two other projects are about to submit data (*Tracers and dispersion of gaseous pollutants* and *UWERN urban meteorology*). And two have already submitted a large amount of data (*PUMA* and *Vertical profiles of atmospheric variables*). The last three (*Physicochemistry and toxicity of particulate pollutants*, *Sources and sinks of urban aerosols* and *Particle dispersion in urban street canyons*) are still at a collection or processing stage.

A considerable amount of effort has been put into the support offered to data providers. This type of activity is expected to continue during the next months, including visits to PIs' universities, since most projects will come to an end in the course of 2001 or at the beginning of 2002. The last project end date is March 2003.

A joint paper on the URGENT data management system has been presented by the DMQA Committee at the *XXIInd Urban and Regional Data Management Symposium* (Delft, September 2000) and will be published in the conference proceedings.

A paper on the URGENT Air archive at BADC has been submitted and accepted at the *Air Quality Management* session of the *Third International Conference on Urban Air Quality* (Loutraki, March 2001) organised by the Institute of Physics.

2.12 WP12 COAPEC

Requirements and funds for the data management of the COAPEC thematic programme have been agreed. This programme will examine climate prediction from coupled ocean-atmosphere models. The main BADC involvement will be to extract and distribute a 1000-year control run of the Hadley Centre's climate model. We are liaising with the COAPEC team and will start to extract the data as soon as we have passed Met Office security clearances.

2.13 WP13 Grid

The BADC has been successful in bidding for 0.25SY from CCLRC e-science. This time is being used to bring us up to speed with the grid world, devise a BADC-grid plan and participate in the EU DataGrid project. These spin-up activities will place the BADC on a good footing to submit proposals to both the NERC and CCRLC e-science programmes.

3. Usage statistics

3.1 Usage by data set

The table below shows the number of registered users of the various data sets as of January 2001, the approximate size of the data sets and the number and size of the data transfers for calendar year 2000. * in the users column indicates public access data sets.

Data set	Users	Dataset Size (MB)	Number of files transferred	Data transferred (MB)
Ugamp-o3	*	80	849	928
Isamsl2	30	2000	198	1
Isamsl3	*	2000	15339	2079
Ecmwf-op	329	200000	208414	261468
Cira	*	3	2527	75
Export	13	70	217	142
Meteosat	*	4000	3773	114
Ukmo-synop	360	4000	3427	466
Claesl3	*	10000	140488	20691
Ukmo-gosta/ Gosta CD	111/68	1000	8918	25424
Acsoe	90	4000	12366	1621
Ukmo-mrf	19	5000	719	15
Ukmo-clim	387	3000	5343	2080
Lims	*	900	92	2
Urgent	16	50	4491	237
Ecmwf-era	291	800000	244097	445140
Ukmo-aam	*	6	2633	70
Ukmo-rad	353	30000	1815186	48921
Toms	*	2000	148010	12214
jet2000	7	700	333	633
Ukmo-assim	174	20000	178640	328577
Haloel2	49	30000	2794	10485
Utlis	28	500	11319	1923
Haloel3	*	500	70036	377
Gome	30	1000	4407	1397
misl3	*9	5000	320304	46952
Ecmwf-trj	357	30000	2357	2666
Soapex	20	14	2134	268
Hyrex	*8	90000	1964	71
Ukmo-surface	673	30000	796155	90208
esa-wv	*	6	538	221
Mst	*4	100000	147237	72681
Ukmo-tovs	119	10000	2589	5075
Virtem	*	300	583	55

3.2 Registered users

The growth in registered users is still increasing. The most notable feature is the continuing shift of the BADC user base to non-atmospheric disciplines such as ecology.

User growth according to registration type.

4. Resources

4.1 Finance

Finance will be presented in an additional paper.

4.2 Staff

The BADC staff allocation in 2000/2001 is as follows:

Dr Bryan Lawrence	Head	50% Management 50% Research
Dr Sam Pepler	Project Scientist, responsible for day-to-day integrity of BADC.	100% BADC
Dr Anne De Rudder	Data Scientist, responsible for URGENT and other chemistry data.	100% BADC
Dr Jamie Kettleborough	Research Scientist, management role for UTLS and Trajectory Service	10% BADC
Ms Anabelle Menochet	Data Scientist, responsible for user support and UKMO data acquisition.	100% BADC
Mr Andrew Harwood	Programmer, responsible for database infrastructure	70% BADC
50% Appointment Pending, 50% Dr Lesley Gray	Research Scientist (AMDI funding line)	100% Research
Short Term Appointment Pending	Further User Support and Met Data Access Support.	100% BADC
Dr Kevin Marsh	Data Scientist, responsible for UTLS programme	100% UTLS/BADC (from Oct)
Mr Peter Chiu	System Manager	40% BADC
Mr Chris Robey	System Maintenance and Backup	30% BADC
Mr Chris Harrold	CAST	100% (from Nov)

The current structure is depicted in the following organogram. Core funding supports those staff in the shaded boxes plus the Head, the AMDI research position, and the system support staff.

BADC Staff at the end of 2000.

4.3 Hardware

A schematic of the BADC hardware based at RAL is shown below:

It shows the following major components:

- **Tornado:** Compaq ES40, dual alpha 500, 1GB memory, 3 internal disk racks filled with 18GB disks. Dat drive, Exabyte drive, CDROM. Two further processors on order.
- **Cirrus:** Sun Ultra60, 300MHz, 256MB memory, Dat drive, CDROM.
- **Disk Box:** 6 x 18GB disk, UltraSCSI
- **RAID Array:** 2 Transtec RAID arrays, each 14 x 50GB disks (600 GB User space: total of 1.2TB), UltraSCSI, dual controller
- **Tape Library:** Qualstar TLS46120 tape library, contains 3AIT-2 drives, 120 slots
- **CD Tower:** Axis storepoint CDROM tower. 6 Nacamichi auto-changer drives (contains 25 CDs)
- **Switch:** 3COM 100baseT switch
- **Other:** Staff PCs and AMD Workstations.

Additionally the BADC now has a HP workstation within the Met Office with an AIT-2 tape drive. This is used to transfer UM and other bulky Met Office data sets to the BADC via the postal service.

Initially four Transtec RAID units were installed however these failed to meet the specifications required. Two have been returned and the other two bought at a discounted rate. The shortfall in disk space will be made up by buying a UK Workstations BulkServer, which will provide about 1TB of disk space.

Extra processors and memory are on order for the BADC's main server.

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NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL

DIRECTORATE OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

ATMOSPHERIC SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY BOARD

BRITISH ATMOSPHERIC DATA CENTRE (BADC) STEERING COMMITTEE

Agenda Item 5. Data Centres Review.

The feedback from the BADC Review of October 2000 to the DC Review is enclosed, for information.

NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL

SCIENCE PROGRAMMES DIRECTORATE

Review

of the

BRITISH ATMOSPHERIC DATA CENTRE

2 October 2000

CONFIDENTIAL

NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL

SCIENCE PROGRAMMES DIRECTORATE

Review of the British Atmospheric Data Centre (BADC)

Held at the Rutherford-Appleton Laboratory on 2nd October 2000

Unconfirmed Report

Review Panel

Professor P Jones	Chair, Climate Research Unit, University of East Anglia
Dr M Jones	British Oceanographic Data Centre
Dr K Law	University of Cambridge and NERC UTLS-OZONE programme
Mr A Cumbria	National Climate Data Center, Asheville, USA
Mr N R Collins	NERC
Dr C H Dimmer	NERC, Secretary

1. Role

The Panel should examine the performance of the BADC over the last five years, assess the proposal for continued funding and make recommendations to the NERC Science and Technology Board on the future operation of BADC, including the level of resources required.

2. Introduction

The BADC has operated under Service Level Agreements (SLAs) between the Rutherford-Appleton Laboratory (RAL) and NERC since 1994. The current SLA is due to expire at the end of March 2001. NERC requires an independent review of the last five years of operation and an assessment of an application for an extension for a further five years. The Review Panel was constituted specifically to carry out these two tasks. The Panel met once at RAL on 2 October 2000. The day started with a short closed session, at which the Panel decided how it would work and discussed general issues concerning BADC. This was followed by a presentation of the Review Report by Dr Bryan Lawrence (Head of BADC) and Dr Lesley Gray (previous Head of BADC). The Panel then toured the facility to meet staff, and received a demonstration of the BADC web site by Dr Sam Pepler. At the end of the morning the Panel reconvened in closed session to discuss and grade the report. The afternoon session consisted of a presentation of the new proposal by Drs Lawrence and Gray, followed by a closed session for the Panel to grade the proposal. At the end of the afternoon Drs Lawrence and Gray were given feedback on the Panel's conclusions and recommendations.

This Report will be provided as input to the NERC Review of Data Centres, which in turn will report to NERC Science and Technology Board in February 2001.

3. Review of the BADC Report for the period 1 April 1996 to September 2000

The Panel considered the Report in detail. The Terms of Reference (Annex 1) formed the basis for the discussion and assessment. The Panel's conclusions are summarised by the following lists of strengths and weaknesses.

3.1 Strengths

1. An excellent service for the level of resources invested.

2. A dedicated Atmospheric Science (AS) data centre is ideal for quality assurance and to appreciate the science involved in producing and interpreting the datasets stored.
3. BADC has solved the distribution problems for the UK Meteorological Office (UKMO) data, which is now available free to the *bona fide* academic researchers globally. The BADC also ensures that European Centre for Medium-range Forecasts (ECMWF) data is available to *bona fide* UK academic researchers.
4. BADC provides safe data archiving for thematic programme data, ensuring continuity of data access regardless of staff changes at the source institution.
5. BADC initiated user survey had produced very positive feedback. In particular, users were enthusiastic about free and rapid access to data, and rapid user assistance.
6. BADC has been at the forefront of online data access and provision, and has taken the lead in NERC data cataloguing in this area.
7. Provision of some data in Excel format to provide ease of access for many users without programming experience. This is particularly popular with non-AS community.

3.2 Weaknesses

The Panel found that only two of the responsibilities outlined in the NERC Data Policy Handbook had not been adequately fulfilled: data archaeology; and promotion of the centre's work.

1. Data archaeology is labour intensive and requires considerable effort on quality control. BADC had applied for additional funds from the SEEDCORN initiative, but had been unsuccessful. There is believed to be a considerable volume of atmospheric chemistry field data that is not lodged with BADC at present, and this could be sought out through a data archaeology initiative. However, the Panel recognised that available resources had severely limited the aspirations of BADC in this area. The Panel suggested that the BADC should first identify the datasets currently held in the community, which may need 'rescuing' or lodging with the BADC. Without such a list it is difficult to appreciate the extent of the data archaeology problem, set priorities or request extra funding.
2. Now that BADC is operating well, more emphasis on publicity is required to promulgate the facilities and services BADC has to offer. **Publicity should be restricted to the UK community otherwise international demand might overwhelm the capability of the Data Centre.**

3.3 Grading

The Panel agreed that the standard alpha scale used for research grants would be inappropriate and that a scale similar to that used for grant reports would be more useful. It was decided to use the following five point grading scale: Excellent, Very Good, Good, Disappointing, Unsatisfactory.

The Panel was very impressed by the level of achievement attained by BADC, with limited resources. A grade of Excellent had only been missed by the narrowest margin, mainly because of the weaknesses outlined above. The Panel strongly commended the BADC for the way in which they have turned around their operation from serving the needs of the stratospheric community to the broader NERC atmospheric research community.

Agreed Grade: Very Good (broadly similar to Alpha 4)

4. Evaluation of the BADC proposal for continued funding for the period 1 April 2001 to 31 March 2006.

4.1 Summary

The Review Panel strongly recommended a funding increase to £660K per annum (pa) to support two extra staff members and to continue support for the Collaboratory for Atmospheric Science and Technology (CAST) initiative. The Panel stipulated that this increase in funding should include increased time to be spent on data centre liaison, publicity and data archaeology. They also stipulated the increased funding should cover a pilot study on the proposed Data Access for Earth System Science (DAFESS) project. The funding increase should also include the £10K pa requested as a contribution towards the RAL Spring School. This would enable BADC to contribute to the course and raise awareness of its existence and facilities. The Panel requested a revised budget with staff roles clearly laid out. This has been included at Annex 1.

4.2 DAFESS issues

Through the DAFESS project the BADC propose to investigate the establishment of a seamless Earth system science data network built on the existing NERC data centres, including access to the surface Earth observation data required by the atmospheric community. They plan to investigate the possibilities for GRID initiatives, particularly GRID enabled data access. This would involve putting the atmospheric and for example, oceanographic datasets into appropriately configured data formats and databases that will allow the community to explore GRID related technologies. As part of the pilot project the BADC should be tasked with organising a Town meeting to test community interest in the DAFESS idea. A full bid should involve all the NERC Data Centres.

5. Issues Arising and Recommendations

1. There are problems associated with continuity of sufficient funding from thematic programmes. Some programmes such as the Chemical Composition of the Upper Troposphere and Lower Stratosphere at Middle Latitudes (UTLS-OZONE) programme have allocated funds to BADC for data provision and storage, while other programmes have no formal arrangements. Funding from Thematic programmes might often provide less support than a full-time post and then only for a limited time period, creating problems for continuity of staff employment. However, if NERC continues to support atmospheric science at or above the current level, there should be a series of programmes coming forward with a requirement for BADC support. The Panel suggested that it should be a requirement that new thematic programmes use the BADC and provide resources for data management. Involvement is essential from the start of a programme, particularly to predict staff requirements and user needs. Links with programmes are/would be strengthened and improved by having either a member of BADC staff, or the BADC Steering Committee (SC), on the steering committee of each Thematic programme generating or needing atmospheric data. It is recommended that NERC should review the membership of programme steering committees to ensure that data issues are appropriately represented.
2. Access to UKMO data is through an ancient IBM front-end, which results in a lengthy process consisting of mainly writing to tapes. An automatic process is required, but this puts high demands on UKMO resources and the UKMO are unable to invest much staff time to assist the BADC. The Panel suggested a requirement for high level liaison between NERC and the UKMO, as NERC is obviously saving the UKMO considerable staff time by diverting meteorological data queries to the BADC.

3. The BADC was encouraged to interact with other data centres, both UK and overseas, however other centres have very different modes of operation. For example, data collectors need to submit data to the BADC in the correct specified format, whereas the British Oceanographic Data Centre (BODC) allocates considerable effort and resources to working up, quality controlling, reformatting and assembling datasets from ships. The BADC should not expect to duplicate data stored by other centres, but should maintain up-to-date links to data sources. A summer vacation student is employed annually to update the BADC links. The BADC should encourage representatives from other international data centres to visit the BADC, for example the US National Climate Data Centre.
4. The Panel encouraged the BADC to communicate with and establish firm links with the University of East Anglia Climate Research Unit, and the Hadley Centre at the UKMO, with regard to archiving climate data.
5. The Panel recommended that the BADC should establish links with the atmospheric science related JIF funded university consortium groups such as the Instrumented Aircraft Facility and Universities Facility for Atmospheric Measurements (UFAM) groups.
6. The Panel recognised that funding for infrastructure improvements is vital, particularly to accommodate increased data storage requirements expected in the future. Provision for off-site storage of data back-ups is poor at present. Currently NERC data is backed-up on CDs and tapes that are stored in a fireproof safe, but better provision needs to be made and sufficient resources allocated.
7. BADC staff employed through RAL cost NERC approximately £50K pa, plus 10% administrative overhead, per staff member. All BADC staff will soon be on open-ended appointments. Although it can be difficult to find and retain staff with experience in atmospheric science, they are likely to interact more easily with users and may spot potential problems more quickly.
8. It has been difficult to maintain staff continuity, as atmospheric scientists are often keen to pursue research aspirations, and eventually cease to find the work challenging. The BADC are therefore keen to provide their staff with research opportunities in addition to data management tasks. Staff with research experience are able to add value to datasets, for example by writing plotting programmes.
9. Queries from non-NERC supported users take up considerable staff time. The Review Panel suggested that certain users, such as schools could be directed to the UKMO's own Web site for access to weather/climate data. There is also much relevant information on the Hadley Centre and the University of East Anglia Climate Research Unit web sites.
10. Staff job profiles in terms of time spent on various different activities are currently inaccurately defined. The Panel suggested that staff effort should be logged on at least a monthly basis.
11. It was recommended that the BADC should determine how many registered users are active, as opposed to non-active users. This information may enable the cost effectiveness of the different datasets to be determined in the future.
12. BADC should try to obtain feedback on the number of papers and PhD theses published using BADC data. BADC could set up a Web accessible form to obtain this feedback from users, although substantial resources should not be allocated to this issue.

- Abstract*
13. The services that BADC can offer have not been widely publicised, and the Panel recommended that the centre could be better advertised, particularly in the UK but also to overseas researchers. However, extensive overseas usage requires international partners to cache data and could lead to a level of demand that BADC would be unable to meet without additional resources. The Royal Meteorological Society could be asked to distribute a questionnaire to its members to raise awareness of the BADC. The Panel recommended that the BADC should clearly advertise what UKMO and ECMWF data was available to overseas researchers.
 14. The BADC should still concentrate its efforts on data archiving, as facilitation of data access is worthless without appropriate archiving.
 15. When instigating data archaeology work, the BADC should consider the potential future usage of the datasets. The process should be selective and should exclude outdated, inaccurate or poorly documented datasets.
 16. The Review Panel commented that BADC SC was dominated by Reading staff, and recommended that the next Chair should not be a Reading University employee.
 17. Although it is difficult to assess the economic benefit of the BADC to the UK, there are obvious benefits to the taxpayer, for example, research on extreme weather prediction using BADC data. The provision of UKMO and ECMWF data via BADC is much more cost effective than the alternate where individual scientists approach the UKMO or ECMWF for specific data needs.
 18. It was recommended that NERC should be more proactive in encouraging award holders to make more use of DATA Centres. For example, the grant application form might be modified to include a section on data centre needs, including the type and amount of data it is expected to be generate.
 19. The BADC suggestion of a pre-print depositing facility was not popular with the Panel, as they felt that many journal articles were already available ahead of publication, through journals' web pages.

Annex 1: Terms of Reference

The Panel is asked to carry out the following tasks.

- i) Evaluate the performance and output of BADC over the period 1 April 1996 to present based on the five-year Report and other relevant material.
- ii) Assess extent to which the recommendations set out in the Report of the BADC Task Force (11 November 1995) have been achieved.
- iii) Assess the management of BADC and the role of the Steering Committee over the last five years.
- iv) Evaluate the use made of BADC by its user community, eg datasets lodged, use of data held at BADC, etc.
- v) Assess the importance of the provision of Meteorological Office data to the atmospheric and wider communities.
- vi) Consider the performance of BADC in terms of the NERC data policy.
- vii) Comment on the value for money offered by BADC.
- viii) Evaluate the proposal for continued funding for the period 1 April 2001 to 31 March 2006, including the level of resources (both fiscal and human) sought.
- ix) Report its findings and recommendations to the NERC Science and Technology Board (February 2001) through the NERC Review of Data Centres.

November 2000

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NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL

DIRECTORATE OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

ATMOSPHERIC SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY BOARD

BRITISH ATMOSPHERIC DATA CENTRE (BADC) STEERING COMMITTEE

Agenda Item 6. NERC Metadata Gateway.

BADC has inherited the maintenance of the NERC Metadata Gateway. While the present funding is sufficient to ensure its current functioning, further funding should be considered, especially in the context of BADC's future involvement in GRID.

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Agenda Item 7. Overview of current topical matters by BADC staff.

Members of the BADC staff will give brief accounts on selected topics (five 10-minute presentations).